

COVID^X

Apply to the Clinical Event on the 23rd of June

COVID^X DATA vs COVID-19 GAME ON

THE HOST **Karolinska Institutet**

CLINICAL EVENT
23 JUNE 2022
9:00 - 13:00 CEST, ONLINE

TOPICS:
Challenges and AI tools in Healthcare systems
COVID Management and lessons learned in medicine

APPLY NOW

Speakers:
David Zakim
Sabine Koch
Carl Johan Sundberg
John Ovretveit (KI)
and
Vicente Estrada (SERMAS)

Join us on the **23rd of June (09:00 AM - 1:00 PM CEST)** for this clinical event organised by Karolinska Institutet, with the participation of SERMAS and Humanitas.

We will discuss the challenges the pandemic has presented to the healthcare sector and lessons learned from its management. We will have high-level speakers from the healthcare domain talking about relevant topics, particularly how AI can support healthcare.

→Check the full agenda and register [here](#).

[Register](#)

Watch the interview with KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET clinical ambassador

"I would say that the collaboration of companies and healthcare providers was enhanced through this program.", Sokratis Nifakos, KAROLINSKA INSTITUTET (KI), one of the COVID-X clinical

Learn more about the Game Changer LOMT working with Humanitas!

Get to know more about LOMT within the #COVIDXSuccessStories! A software for COVID-19 mass testing extending the standard processes of molecular testing for SARS-CoV-2 RNA with

partners.

advanced data analytics and
pool testing.

[Interview](#)

[Read](#)

Our collaborators

We work with a range of parallel projects in common areas of research to maximise our impact and network reach. Check out their June events.

[Check the events](#)

COVID-X

www.covid-x.eu / info@covid-x.eu

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